

LEARNING ENGLISH WITH CANVAS

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INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic took the world by surprise.

Globally, everything has stopped. Projects have been delayed, workplaces closed and schools shut down. The world seems to have ground to a halt because of the novel coronavirus.

However, students continue their education through online learning and via video calls with their teachers. The model is currently the best alternative as keeping schools open poses a safety risk for students.

WHAT IS CANVAS?

Canvas is a web-based learn management system, or LMS. It is used by learning institutions, educators, and students to access and manage online course learning materials and communicate about skill development and learning achievement.

Canvas includes a variety of customizable course creation and management tools, course and user analytics and statistics, and internal communication tools.

Institutions may provide users with a Canvas account, or individual users can try the free version by signing up for their own account.

WHY CANVAS?

There are lots of reasons to be excited about Canvas. In addition to a clean, user-friendly interface, Canvas offers tools that instructors can use to save time and to enhance teaching and learning:

- [SpeedGrader](#) saves time by allowing instructors to view submitted assignments online and then annotate, comment, and assign grades to groups or individuals.
- The [Canvas calendar](#) helps your students stay on track by displaying all course assignments and events together in one place.
- Canvas offers mobile functionality. There's a Canvas app for your [Android](#) or [iOS](#) device. And because the platform was built using responsive design, it works well in most mobile web browsers.
- Canvas integrates with external tools, such as [ComPAIR](#), a peer review application that encourages constructive criticism, critical thinking, and self-reflection.

PRO AND CONS

Pro

- Simple and user friendly user interface.
- Third-party solution integration.
- Ease of course management.
- Inbuilt discussion forum.

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Cons

- Lack of inbuilt video conferencing tools.
- Quizzes should have proctoring and browser locked capability.
- Mobile app can get have glitches.
- Notifications are missed at times.

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That's all we can say now. If u curious more about canvas, try to use it and feel the different

